

LIDAR quality performance report

ARSF Data Analysis Node

Executive Summary of calibration flight

- Data have been collected from a Leica ALS50-II LIDAR and processed to point-cloud level
- Accuracy of elevations from calibration flight data, checked against GCPs, range from:
 - Mean error magnitude of 2cm with standard deviation of 2cm for flights of 1350m altitude
 - Mean error magnitude of 7.1cm with standard deviation 6.2cm for flights of 2350m altitude
 - Elevations from 2350m altitude flight data are consistently lower than 1350m data by an average difference of approximately 8cm.
- Geolocation accuracy checked against vectors show variable shifts ranging from 1m to 10m. Geolocation checked against GCPs show no discernible shift, which suggests there may be inaccuracies or projection issues with the vectors.
- It is recommended that GCPs are collected for all survey sites to get the highest quality products

Summary

This report describes experience with the LIDAR data processing software based on a week training session in Heerbrugg, Switzerland and the LIDAR calibration flight during the week commencing 15th September 2008. It also presents results on the accuracies achieved using the software with the calibration flights.

Software

A data processing and software flow diagram is shown in Figure 1.

Leica Software

The software supplied by Leica for taking the raw scan data and creating a point cloud is relatively straight forward to use. It is MS Windows based with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and is currently unable to be automated. It is capable of processing all flight lines from a single project as a batch job. The default output for the point cloud is in the binary LAS format but it is also possible to output in ASCII format. The data can be output in UTM and UK OSTN02 (British National grid) projections, amongst others. Figure 2 shows an example of the mapped point cloud product.

QC Software

The 3rd party (*Bentley Microstation + TerraScan*) software is used for in-depth QC-ing of the data although for quick overviews of the flight lines it is easier to view the data in the free PointVUE software. For typical projects the software will be used to see how well flight lines match up together, plotting cross sections of flight lines, checking elevations and doing some classification (or filtering) of noisy points. Other minor post-processing routines may also take place.

In some circumstances multiple iterations of the processing may be needed (especially during calibration/boresight missions).

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the LIDAR data processing chain.

Figure 2: Example of the LIDAR pointcloud mapped at 0.40m pixel resolution. Left shows a sample of the intensity and right shows the uncalibrated elevations for the same area.

Results

The data from the calibration flight have been processed and the conclusions are as follows.

The boresight corrections aligned the images to within the recommended levels (approximately 20cm variation in elevation prior to range correction is typical). Profiles of the data appeared to agree to within this level.

After range corrections have been applied, the elevation variation improved (excluding the flights over 2300m altitude) to within a local range of approximately 10cm. Compared to the ground control points (which have not been used for the range corrections) the average error is about 2cm with a standard deviation also of 2cm. Including the points from flights with altitude greater than 2300m, the range of elevation variation of the points is of the order of 30cm-35cm. These data have consistently lower elevation values than the other LIDAR points. These data points, checked against the GCPs, gave an average error magnitude of 7.1cm with a standard deviation of 6.2cm. Profiles of the data can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Ordnance Survey vector maps have been used as a check to the geolocation accuracy. Four flights at the 1350m altitude (one of each flown N, S, E and W) have been mapped to a 1m grid and compared to vectors. The results are mixed; parts of the images appear to match the vectors within 1m, while other parts show errors of up to 10m. Figures 4a and 4b show screen shots of 2 regions for the 4 flight lines.

Figure 3: Profiles of the calibrated data. Red points correspond to flight lines at 750m, blue to 1350m flight lines and yellow to 2300m flight lines. Top profile is across a rooftop, middle profile is along a section of runway and the bottom profile is another section of tarmac.

Figure 4a: Vectors vs LIDAR data – West side of airfield. Geolocation appears to agree to within 1-2 pixels equivalent to 1-2m for all flight lines. No obvious deviations between flight direction suggest boresight parameters are good.

Figure 4b: Vectors vs LIDAR data – North East side of airfield. Offsets of 5-10m are present in this area of the image, in the same direction for each flight line.

The nature of the vector offsets suggest that there may be a mapping error between the vectors and LIDAR data. Ground control points have been used as a secondary check against the accuracy of the

LIDAR and vector data. Errors in the GCP located positions and vector positions have been noted for 5 areas of the calibration site. The results show that the GCPs are located to within 1-2m of their positions, whilst the vectors are located to within 1-7m of their positions. This can be seen in Figures A1-A5 in the Appendix of this report. This is an ongoing investigation.

The Leica support team have agreed to check our calibration to see if the parameters look correct. The high altitude flight data do not appear to perform as well as the other data, which could be due to the issues noted below.

Surface Test

Two of the flight lines (one NS and one EW flown at 1350m) have been used to generate surfaces so as to see more clearly how the lines match up. A surface has been generated from each of the flight lines' data and also from the combined data. A profile has been taken along the same transect for the individual surfaces and can be seen in Figure 5. The same has been done for the surface created by the combined data sets and is shown in Figure 6, along with a zoomed section of the shaded surface in Figure 7.

Figure 5: Profiles of two surfaces created by LIDAR data from two flight lines. Surface from flight line 2 is approximately 5cms lower than the surface from flight line 1 data.

Figure 6: Profile of the surface generated by combining LIDAR data from flight lines 1 and 2. Note how it is noisier than either of the surfaces 1 and 2 as it is influenced by them both.

Figure 7: Zoomed section of the combined surface. The area where the flight lines overlap can clearly be seen by the “saw tooth” effect.

The combined surface appears noisier than the others because of the elevation differences between the two LIDAR data sets. The influence of these differences can be seen as the “saw tothing” in Figure 7. The elevation difference due to the “saw teeth” is about 6cm .

Issues

Two issues arose during the processing of the calibration data.

1. The high altitude flights were affected by haze: a second surface approximately 200m above the terrain is apparent on the processed LIDAR data. These points have been removed from the datasets, but as a result there is a less dense network of points on the ground. As a consequence, these datasets have not directly been used to identify the calibration parameters, but have still been used to check the quality.
2. The majority of the ground control points fall outside the ± 7 degree swath of the 750m altitude flights. This has meant that the 1350m flight data has been used to range correct the data. Leica recommends to use the 750m altitude data for range correcting to get the best results.

Flight recommendations

For the next calibration flight it is recommended to fly the EW 750m flight line about 100m further South to get the runway (with the GCPs on) within the swath. Also, to fly 4 flight lines at this altitude (i.e. NS, SN, EW and WE) to increase the chance of getting the GCPs within the ± 7 degree swath.

To deliver the best quality data possible we would need some ground survey points to be collected locally at each site, particularly over areas of hard, flat concrete or tarmac. This may not be possible (or feasible) for the majority of sites to be surveyed. PI's should be made known of this in the application procedure, giving them the option to supply GCP's at the time of processing. It *MAY* be the case that the GCP's do not need to be local to the survey site, but that an extra flight line of data captured (per flight) over the calibration site could be used. This would not be as good as using local GCPs since local effects – such as those due to atmospheric conditions – would not be taken into account, but it may help correct against systematic errors in the LIDAR data. This is not a substitute for having accurate local GCPs.

Appendix – Results of GCP, Vector and LIDAR data comparisons.

Vectors have been overlaid onto the LIDAR data to ascertain the accuracy of the LIDAR geolocation. Due to some (major) differences in the vector/LIDAR data, GCPs have been used as a secondary check to the geolocation. Five areas of the calibration site where GCPs are available have been selected to compare the vector and GCP data to the LIDAR data. The table and figures below show the errors between vector and LIDAR, and GCP and LIDAR.

Area	Approximate vector error (metres)	Approximate GCP error (metres)
East Cross	7	1
West Cross	1 - 2	1 - 2
North Cross	3 - 4	1
Intersection	2	1
Basestation square	1	1

Figure A1 – East cross: GCPs are shown as green crosses and vectors as yellow lines. GCPs appear to be located correctly (within 1m) whilst vectors show a 7m offset.

Figure A2 – West cross: GCPs are shown as green crosses and vectors as yellow lines. GCPs appear to be located correctly (within 1-2m) and vectors show a 1-2m offset.

Figure A3 – North cross: GCPs are shown as green crosses and vectors as yellow lines. GCPs appear to be located correctly (within 1m) and vectors show a 3-4m offset.

Figure A4 – Intersection: GCPs are shown as green crosses and vectors as yellow lines. GCPs appear to be located correctly (within 1m) whilst vectors show a 1-2m offset.

Figure A5 – Basestation square: GCPs are shown as green crosses and vectors as yellow lines. Both the GCPs and vector data appear to be located correctly to within 1-2m.